

INNOVATION IN DEFENSE: CHALLENGES AND POSSIBILITIES FOR THE BRAZILIAN SYSTEM

Authors:

Ana Luiza Bravo e Paivaⁱ

Karina Furtado Rodriguesⁱⁱ

POLICY STATEMENT

In its planning for the Future War, what can Brazil learn from military powers to improve its defense innovation system? Throughout the text, we will try to present how the country in question has positioned itself in the face of challenges related to the modernization of the defense sector. Therefore, based on theoretical reflection on the subject, possible actions to be incorporated into the Brazilian defense innovation system will be listed. As a result, it was found that the lack of public investment in research and development, institutional-bureaucratic rigidity, and little interference from the Ministry of Defense in the performance and prioritization of projects in the Armed Forces are elements that compromise our ability to think about the present and even more, the future.

BACKGROUND

Great powers are already thinking about the future of war, and based on the understanding that innovation is essential to stay ahead in deterrence, they have been investing heavily in developing a thought about the future of war to guide their transformation processes. What can Brazil, a middle power, far from the possibility of interstate conflicts, learn from the practices of the United States and France? Also, what are the current institutional barriers in Brazil to changes aimed at meeting this demand for preparation for future conflicts? These are the two objectives of this policy brief.

For countries that are not powers, such as Brazil, thinking about the Future War is something quite new. However, innovation, which is the basic condition for thinking about the future, is already quite present in the Brazilian military imaginary and has a vast international academic production, and some national, despite its difficult implementation.

There are many theories about innovation generally applied to the military environment. One of the most widespread is the Triple Helix theory. For it, the three vertices of innovation would be the State, the Market, and the Universities and research institutes. An important contribution of this literature was to propose another way other than the market-state dyad, as the trilateral relationship moderates these tendencies by introducing possibilities for mediation, coalition building, and indirect link (1). According to the aforementioned authors, the Triple Helix model suggests the creation of hybrid institutions within each of the dyadic relationships within the triad.

According to Robert Atkinson (2), the concept of innovation system proposed in the literature is limited, as existing concepts consider only the elements related to promoting science and technology, without considering the political, economic, and social factors affecting innovation. One of them considers that, conceptually, the factors that influence the ability of a particular country to innovate can be organized into what is defined as the "innovation success triangle" (3), that is when there is synergy and full functioning of the business environment, the regulatory environment, and the innovation scenario.

Before reflecting on the innovation system, institution, or goal, therefore, it is necessary to consider not only the inherent issues of the transfer itself but also the specificities of the defense sector. Using military jargon, these actions towards innovation in defense are referred to as "military transformation" or "revolution in military affairs," whose purpose would be to leverage the deterrent capacity of a country's Armed Forces in a shorter period (4). However, despite the great historical importance of the defense sector for innovation, its importance is reduced in times of peace. Consequently, the dilemma of justifying military spending emerges, where others such as health, education, and infrastructure are the subject of high demand from society groups (5).

To analyze the role of the industry in defense innovation, it is also necessary to consider the characteristics of the Defense market. Unlike other sectors, its main characteristic is the monopsony, which is the term given to markets where there is only one buyer and few sellers (6). This type of market implies a great dependence of companies on a single buyer, which is the government, making the responsibility of States for the defense industry intrinsic to the sector.

In addition to the monopsony, there are significant barriers to entry in this type of market. Because it is highly specific and technical, companies need constant contact with specialized military bureaucracy, characterized by a high level of insulation^{III} (7). It is no wonder that many of these companies hire retired military personnel for institutional communication-related positions (8). This ends up generating a cultural militarization of exchange relations between these companies, which can be another limiting factor. Additionally, the commercialization of defense products depends not only on companies - there are international treaties that regulate the market, and the positioning of governments can also interfere with the intention of other nationalities to buy.

The defense industrial base (DIB) of a country is the set of companies that provide products for the sector. The concept of "defense product" is broad and can include very different goods and services, such as products consumed by the military - such as food, clothing, and medicine; non-lethal strategic products - such as vehicles and fuel; and lethal systems of various types, ranging from small arms to high-potential weapons (9).

These companies, in order to remain competitive, need constant contact with the Science, Technology, and Innovation (ST&I) sector, which requires high investment and maintenance costs. In a context where revenues from the state are uncertain, companies that make up a DIB have therefore developed survival strategies. There is a process of diversification and downsizing within defense industrial bases, as well as acceptance of international companies and the creation of joint ventures to develop these products (10).

This context makes the development of a DIB for less developed countries much more difficult, as it has a high maintenance cost. However, even for underdeveloped countries, there are cases where this high

investment has occurred despite their social and economic situation. Leske (2015) points out that reasons for this are the arms race, high technology production, investment in dual-use technologies, and spin-off effects. Another factor that creates difficulties is a lack of measurement of how military spending on Research & Development (R&D) can drive the generation of new technologies in DIB companies, precisely because of the high technological level that the sector requires.

Regarding the possible nature of Defense innovations, it can be distinguished into two types: technological, i.e., defense products and their manufacturing processes, and non-technological, i.e., doctrinal, institutional, organizational, strategic, and tactical principles (11). From the perspective presented by Azevedo (2013), this study sought to guide the empirical analysis of non-technological aspects, highlighting the doctrinal and organizational nature.

When we think of Brazil, innovation and future warfare can only be thought of if we take into account these above-mentioned relationships between State, market, university, or even the innovation success triangle. It is insufficient to analyze only military organizations; one must look at the entire innovation environment of the country. Brazil, for example, ranks 66th in the Global Innovation Ranking, behind other Latin American countries such as Uruguay, Mexico, and Costa Rica, and scoring only 33 out of 100 possible points in the assessment. The evaluation shows that Brazil's institutional and regulatory environment is far from what innovation theories advocate (12). The lack of a national development plan, a low level of investment in general and in the defense sector, as well as a history of recurring economic and political crises, contribute to the low performance in the ranking.

The conception of the defense innovation system in Brazil has a relevant milestone in the approval of the National Defense Strategy (END), during the Lula government. This document mentions, for the first time in Brazilian history, the relationship between innovation and DIB, outlining a plan for its development. Brazil has a defense innovation system called SIS-Def, which is composed of both public and private actors. Its agents are the Defense Industrial Base (DIB), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), military, and funding agencies (13).

Leske's research (2015) shows that 81% of the responding Brazilian Defense Industry companies have implemented some kind of innovation because of their relationship with the Armed Forces. Only a third of these companies have any interaction with Higher Education Institutions, and only 25% of them had interactions with Technological Institutes and Centers. Offset contracts are the rarest, with only 14% of the companies having had this type of contract. The majority of the 45 companies analyzed by the author also stated that they do not have government funding aimed at innovation, despite the existence of funds such as FINEP (Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos) and BNDES. Most of these companies are associated with the Brazilian Association of Defense and Security Materials Industries (ABIMDE) - about 200 members, with most of the companies headquartered in the states of São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro, respectively.

Regarding the relationship between universities and the creation of innovations for Defense, since 2005, the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) has played an active role in expanding the Defense theme for academia, with the creation of research funding notices such as Pró-Defesa and Pró-Estratégia. In addition to this, the creation of graduate programs within military schools - such as those existing in Brazilian Command and General Staff College, Naval War College, War College, and Air Force University - reinforces the attempt to bring Defense closer to the University. There

is also greater interaction between the Armed Forces and the University in specific strategic projects, such as the Astros 2020 project being developed by the Army in partnership with the Federal University of Santa Maria. What has been observed in the Brazilian case is that the interfaces between the actors of the triple helix are still very limited.

In terms of organizational structure, each of the singular forces has its own innovation subsystems, not necessarily connected to non-technological innovation subsystems. Within the Ministry of Defense, the body directly linked to the defense innovation environment is the Secretariat for Defense Products (SEPROD), and in the Army, the relatively recent Agency for Technological Management and Innovation (AGITEC) - created in 2015.

Despite the Ministry of Defense's role, planning and procurement for each of the forces are still done separately, preventing joint purchases. One of the Ministry of Defense's main missions should be precisely the coordination and interaction of the three forces, but it has had very little success in this task (14). Furthermore, according to data collected in interviews with members of SEPROD, the entire laboratory structure and MD's promotion of innovation in them is a simple response to the demands of each of the Singular Forces, without any broader discussion of prioritizing certain projects over others, and without considering the interoperability factor.

Despite the advanced discussions on Defense innovation in Brazil, the War of the Future is still a subject little explored by the Armed Forces. In the scope of the Army, there was an initial reflection published by the Strategic Studies Center of the Army (CEEEx) in 2019, within the framework of the Interdisciplinary Project (PI) of the Course of Politics, Strategy, and High Administration of the Army (CPEAEx), which had as its theme "The War of the Future and the Brazilian Army: challenges and opportunities."

The text brings considerations on how to enable the Brazilian Army, considering a temporal horizon of 2035. For this, it considered possibilities of organizational evolution in the face of the constant demand of the Armed Forces' Presence Strategy throughout the Brazilian territory. It is common in Brazilian military environments to use some American acronyms, such as VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity) to designate the scenario of the Future War.

Future conflicts mentioned in the document include "indirect confrontations between major powers; increased asymmetric hybrid confrontations in urban environments; preponderance of air and space domains; increase in actions in the cyber domain; preponderance of the informational environment; increase in systemic warfare; and robotization of the battlefield" (15). In this sense, a national strategy is envisaged to deal with these forthcoming threats, presenting preliminary studies of innovations from other countries. They also prioritize a scale of action, with information superiority being the most important, followed by interoperability, protection, cybernetics, among others. Additionally, the incorporation of technologies such as radiofrequency weapons, robotics, artificial intelligence, satellites, among others, is sought, "with priority given to national and preferably dual-use technologies" (16).

Regarding academic research on the Future War, there is a study group within the Naval War College. In the Army, there is also a current project on the subject within the Military Sciences Postgraduate Program at the Meira Mattos Institute, at Command and General Staff College, which may soon influence strategic documents and be formalized in doctrine.

The new National Defense Policy and proposed National Defense Strategy in 2020 indicate that technological innovation and the development of defense industry base remain the focus of defense actions, highlighting:

“[t]he countries that invest in innovation and produce disruptive technologies will increase their level of development and population well-being, while those that absorb technologies without investing in their own knowledge process, and in the autochthonous modernization of their productive capacities will follow playing a secondary role in the world scenario, without adding benefits to their populations” (17).

CONCLUSIONS

With a view to suggesting innovation policy tools that encompass the future war, aligned with the institutional, political, and economic context of the analyzed case, this section explores aspects of Brazilian military organizational culture, organizational and institutional aspects of foreign measures that differ from the Brazilian context, and possible next steps for Brazil.

Regarding aspects of military organizational culture, important differences between countries must be considered. In particular, the practices of leaner bureaucracies, such as those in the US, should be viewed with caution. This is because both the Brazilian and French bureaucracies contain traces of exaggerated formalism, which considerably slows down the processes of the public machine (18), flexibility essential for innovations to occur.

Beyond the bureaucratic characteristic of military organizations, there are practices and formalities that are very different from the civilian business environment, such as a high valuation and dedication of time to rituals, the constant attempt to minimize uncertainties, respect for rules, and respect for hierarchy (19) - sometimes at the expense of the individual's expertise beyond their rank. Additionally, there are several subcultures within the forces (such as weapons and specialties), which alter the interrelational dynamics of the implementation of innovation policies.

Looking at the US and French cases, organizational structures focused on innovation and defense are identified that try to overcome excessive formalism. This is the case of the French Defense Innovation Agency and the US Defense Innovation Unit, as well as US federal laboratories. In these structures, actors from the civilian world are brought into the innovation process. Thus, such state agencies assume a coordinating role in actions, not executing the entire project, still counting on a flexibility in the forms of project contracting. Therefore, it is suggested that Brazil incorporate into its innovation strategy a structure that has a broad approach to the network of participating institutions, less hierarchical and with a coordinating and catalyzing role in actions - like the aforementioned organizations.

Although in both cases mentioned (the US and France), economic and regulatory environments are quite disparate, a common point observed is the tradition of public investment in research and development. In this sense, the importance of Brazil positioning itself regarding the necessary actions to foster the

development of indigenous defense industries and technologies, as presented in defense document reviews, is reinforced.

Moreover, there is still a tendency not to think in advance about policies that involve the long term, amid so many short-term demands, especially in developing countries (20). Therefore, talking about the future war in Brazil imposes even greater challenges than those presented to the defense field itself.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above discussion, the following paths should be considered for strengthening the defense innovation system in Brazil:

- (1) When importing models and structures for the Brazilian defense innovation system, it is necessary to conduct a careful analysis of the political, economic, and cultural scenarios of both importing and exporting countries.
- (2) The restructuring of defense organizations in Brazil is an essential action to create an environment that fosters interaction between the various actors that make up the defense innovation system, with a focus on government actors at different levels, specialized epistemic communities, as well as the defense industry.
- (3) It is imperative to break the bureaucratic insulation related to defense issues so that they can be discussed by society, as only then will we have the necessary elements to understand the relevance of investing and preparing for the new challenges imposed by the new modalities of conflicts that are emerging in the international scenario.

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ⁱ Faculty member at the Graduate Program in Military Sciences (PPGCM) of the Brazilian Army Command and General Staff School and researcher affiliated with the InterAgency Institute. Email: albepaiva@gmail.com

ⁱⁱ Faculty member at the Graduate Program in Military Sciences (PPGCM) of the Brazilian Army Command and General Staff School and Research Coordinator at the Defense Governance and Public Policy Laboratory. E-mail: karinafrodrigues@gmail.com